

Pathway Analysis Report

This report contains the pathway analysis results for the submitted sample ". Analysis was performed against Reactome version 83 on 03/02/2023. The web link to these results is:

<https://reactome.org/PathwayBrowser/#/ANALYSIS=MjAyMzAyMDMxOTIyNDRfNTkxMw%3D%3D>

Please keep in mind that analysis results are temporarily stored on our server. The storage period depends on usage of the service but is at least 7 days. As a result, please note that this URL is only valid for a limited time period and it might have expired.

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1. Introduction

Reactome is a curated database of pathways and reactions in human biology. Reactions can be considered as pathway 'steps'. Reactome defines a 'reaction' as any event in biology that changes the state of a biological molecule. Binding, activation, translocation, degradation and classical biochemical events involving a catalyst are all reactions. Information in the database is authored by expert biologists, entered and maintained by Reactome's team of curators and editorial staff. Reactome content frequently cross-references other resources e.g. NCBI, Ensembl, UniProt, KEGG (Gene and Compound), ChEBI, PubMed and GO. Orthologous reactions inferred from annotation for Homo sapiens are available for 17 non-human species including mouse, rat, chicken, puffer fish, worm, fly, yeast, rice, and Arabidopsis. Pathways are represented by simple diagrams following an SBGN-like format.

Reactome's annotated data describe reactions possible if all annotated proteins and small molecules were present and active simultaneously in a cell. By overlaying an experimental dataset on these annotations, a user can perform a pathway over-representation analysis. By overlaying quantitative expression data or time series, a user can visualize the extent of change in affected pathways and its progression. A binomial test is used to calculate the probability shown for each result, and the p-values are corrected for the multiple testing (Benjamini-Hochberg procedure) that arises from evaluating the submitted list of identifiers against every pathway.

To learn more about our Pathway Analysis, please have a look at our relevant publications:

Fabregat A, Sidiropoulos K, Garapati P, Gillespie M, Hausmann K, Haw R, ... D'Eustachio P (2016). The reactome pathway knowledgebase. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 44(D1), D481–D487. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkv1351>.

Fabregat A, Sidiropoulos K, Viteri G, Forner O, Marin-Garcia P, Arnau V, ... Hermjakob H (2017). Reactome pathway analysis: a high-performance in-memory approach. *BMC Bioinformatics*, 18.

2. Properties

- This is an **overrepresentation** analysis: A statistical (hypergeometric distribution) test that determines whether certain Reactome pathways are over-represented (enriched) in the submitted data. It answers the question 'Does my list contain more proteins for pathway X than would be expected by chance?' This test produces a probability score, which is corrected for false discovery rate using the Benjamini-Hochberg method. [↗](#)
- 18 out of 24 identifiers in the sample were found in Reactome, where 105 pathways were hit by at least one of them.
- All non-human identifiers have been converted to their human equivalent. [↗](#)
- This report is filtered to show only results for species 'Homo sapiens' and resource 'all resources'.
- The unique ID for this analysis (token) is MjAyMzAyMDMxOTIyNDRfNTkxMw%3D%3D. This ID is valid for at least 7 days in Reactome's server. Use it to access Reactome services with your data.

3. Genome-wide overview

This figure shows a genome-wide overview of the results of your pathway analysis. Reactome pathways are arranged in a hierarchy. The center of each of the circular "bursts" is the root of one top-level pathway, for example "DNA Repair". Each step away from the center represents the next level lower in the pathway hierarchy. The color code denotes over-representation of that pathway in your input dataset. Light grey signifies pathways which are not significantly over-represented.

4. Most significant pathways

The following table shows the 25 most relevant pathways sorted by p-value.

Pathway name	Entities				Reactions	
	found	ratio	p-value	FDR*	found	ratio
Nephrin family interactions	3 / 25	0.002	1.40e-05	0.002	2 / 13	9.19e-04
Sensory processing of sound by outer hair cells of the cochlea	3 / 64	0.004	2.24e-04	0.012	1 / 8	5.65e-04
Sensory processing of sound by inner hair cells of the cochlea	3 / 76	0.005	3.70e-04	0.013	1 / 7	4.95e-04
Sensory processing of sound	3 / 87	0.006	5.48e-04	0.014	2 / 13	9.19e-04
RHO GTPase cycle	5 / 460	0.03	0.001	0.024	10 / 91	0.006
Signaling by Rho GTPases	6 / 709	0.047	0.002	0.024	12 / 203	0.014
Signaling by Rho GTPases, Miro GTPases and RHOBTB3	6 / 725	0.048	0.002	0.024	12 / 212	0.015
Cell-Cell communication	3 / 134	0.009	0.002	0.024	2 / 60	0.004
Molecules associated with elastic fibres	2 / 37	0.002	0.002	0.024	2 / 10	7.07e-04
Elastic fibre formation	2 / 45	0.003	0.003	0.031	2 / 17	0.001
Nuclear signaling by ERBB4	2 / 47	0.003	0.003	0.031	2 / 34	0.002
TGF-beta receptor signaling activates SMADs	2 / 50	0.003	0.004	0.031	2 / 44	0.003
Degradation of DVL	2 / 57	0.004	0.005	0.038	3 / 7	4.95e-04
Transport of connexins along the secretory pathway	1 / 3	1.97e-04	0.005	0.038	1 / 2	1.41e-04
Oligomerization of connexins into connexons	1 / 3	1.97e-04	0.005	0.038	1 / 3	2.12e-04
Negative regulation of TCF-dependent signaling by DVL-interacting proteins	1 / 5	3.28e-04	0.009	0.055	2 / 2	1.41e-04
Signaling by ERBB4	2 / 82	0.005	0.01	0.055	2 / 52	0.004
Regulation of gap junction activity	1 / 6	3.94e-04	0.011	0.055	4 / 4	2.83e-04
SARS-CoV-2 targets PDZ proteins in cell-cell junction	1 / 6	3.94e-04	0.011	0.055	1 / 4	2.83e-04
Signal Transduction	11 / 3,030	0.199	0.014	0.071	35 / 2,532	0.179
Signaling by TGF-beta Receptor Complex	2 / 107	0.007	0.017	0.08	2 / 100	0.007
Formation of annular gap junctions	1 / 11	7.22e-04	0.02	0.08	2 / 2	1.41e-04
WNT mediated activation of DVL	1 / 12	7.87e-04	0.022	0.087	4 / 4	2.83e-04
Gap junction degradation	1 / 12	7.87e-04	0.022	0.087	4 / 4	2.83e-04
Signaling by TGFB family members	2 / 136	0.009	0.026	0.098	2 / 125	0.009

* False Discovery Rate

5. Pathways details

For every pathway of the most significant pathways, we present its diagram, as well as a short summary, its bibliography and the list of inputs found in it.

1. Nephrin family interactions (R-HSA-373753)

Cellular compartments: plasma membrane.

Nephrin (NPHS1) is a member of the Super-IgG-Molecule family and is most prominently expressed in kidney podocytes. It is a major if not the most important structural component of the slit diaphragm, a modified adherens junction inbetween these cells. NPHS1 has an extracellular domain that contains eight distal IgG like domains and one proximal fibronectin type III domain, a transmembrane domain and a short intracellular domain. NPHS1 molecules show both homophilic and heterophilic interactions. Among heterophilic interaction partners, slit diaphragm proteins such as Kin of IRRE-like protein 1 (KIRREL, Nephrin-like protein 1, NEPH1), KIRREL3 (NEPH2) and KIRREL2 (NEPH3) were shown to stabilize the slit diaphragm structure. Intracellularly Podocin (NPHS2), CD2 associated protein (CD2AP) and adherens junction associated proteins like IQGAP, MAGI, CASK and spectrins all interact with NPHS1. Hence it seems to play a major role in organizing the molecular structure of the slit diaphragm itself and via its binding partners links it to the actin cytoskeleton. NPHS1 tyrosine phosphorylation by the Src kinase FYN initiates the PI3K-AKT signaling cascade, which seems to promote antiapoptotic signals.

References

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- Benzing T & Huber TB (2005). The slit diaphragm: a signaling platform to regulate podocyte function. *Curr Opin Nephrol Hypertens*, 14, 211-6. [↗](#)
- Wartiovaara J, Patrakka J & Tryggvason K (2006). Hereditary proteinuria syndromes and mechanisms of proteinuria. *N Engl J Med*, 354, 1387-401. [↗](#)

Holmberg C, Wartiovaara J, Ljungberg P, Lenkkeri U, Jalanko H, Tryggvason K, ... Ruotsalainen V (1999). Nephrin is specifically located at the slit diaphragm of glomerular podocytes. Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A, 96, 7962-7. [↗](#)

Kudlicka K, Zhou H, Lehtonen S, Farquhar MG, Iino N & Ryan JJ (2005). Cell junction-associated proteins IQGAP1, MAGI-2, CASK, spectrins, and alpha-actinin are components of the nephrin multiprotein complex. Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A, 102, 9814-9. [↗](#)

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2008-02-26	Authored	Garapati P V, de Bono B
2008-07-16	Created	Garapati P V
2010-03-01	Edited	Garapati P V
2010-05-20	Reviewed	Grahammer Florian, Huber TB
2022-11-19	Modified	Wright A

2 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 3 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
KIRREL3	Q6UWL6, Q8IZU9	SPTBN1	Q01082

2. Sensory processing of sound by outer hair cells of the cochlea (R-HSA-9662361)

Outer hair cells (OHCs) produce amplification of sound waves in the cochlea by shortening and lengthening in response to sound, a phenomenon called electromotility (reviewed in Kim and Fettiplace 2014, Fettiplace 2016, Fettiplace 2017, Fritzsche et al. 2017, Ashmore 2019). Like inner hair cells, OHCs possess apical stereocilia arranged in rows of ascending height. A taller stereocilium is connected to a shorter stereocilium by a tip link comprising a CDH23 dimer on the side of the taller stereocilium and a PCDH15 dimer on the apex of the shorter stereocilium. PCDH15 interacts with LHFPL5, a subunit of the mechano-electrical transduction channel complex (MET channel, also called the mechanotransduction channel), which contains TMC1 or TMC2, TMIE, CIB2, and LHFPL5 (reviewed in Fettiplace 2016). Deflection of the stereocilia in one direction produces tension on the tip link that increases the open probability of the MET channel, resulting in depolarization of the OHC. Deflection of the stereocilia in the opposite direction produces compression on the tip link that decreases the open probability of the MET channel, resulting in hyperpolarization of the OHC.

Sound causes micromechanical motions of the organ of Corti that result in alternating tension and compression in the tip link that produce excitatory-inhibitory cycles of MET channel openings and closings relative to the MET channel's resting open probability. This causes directionally alternating fluxes of K^+ and Ca^{2+} , yielding depolarization-hyperpolarization cycles that cause conformational changes in prestin (SLC26A5). These cycles are asymmetrical, with contraction caused by depolarization dominating elongation caused by hyperpolarization due to the asymmetry of the open probability of MET channels. Stereociliary ATP2B2 (PMCA2) extrudes calcium ions and basally located KCNQ4 extrudes potassium ions to repolarize the OHC.

Depolarization of the OHC causes a decrease in length of the OHC due to a very rapid, voltage-sensitive change in conformation of the membrane protein prestin (SLC26A5), an unusual member of the anion transporter family located in the lateral membrane (Mahendrasingam et al, 2010) that appears to respond to cytosolic chloride by altering its conformation in the plane of the plasma membrane (reviewed in Dallos et al. 2006, Dallos 2008, Hudspeth 2014, Reichenbach and Hudspeth 2014, Ashmore 2019, Santos-Sacchi 2019). Prestin also appears to act as a weak chloride-bicarbonate antiporter (Mistrik et al. 2012). Changes in length of the OHCs cause movement of the reticular lamina toward and away from the basilar membrane.

References

- Santos-Sacchi J (2019). The speed limit of outer hair cell electromechanical activity. *HNO*, 67, 159-164. [↗](#)
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- Kim KX & Fettiplace R (2014). The physiology of mechano-electrical transduction channels in hearing. *Physiol. Rev.*, 94, 951-86. [↗](#)

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Date	Action	Author
2019-09-23	Edited	May B
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2020-09-14	Reviewed	Furness DN, Dallos P
2020-12-12	Modified	May B

2 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 3 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
SPTBN1	Q01082	TRIOBP	Q9H2D6-4, Q9H2D6-5

3. Sensory processing of sound by inner hair cells of the cochlea (R-HSA-9662360)

Inner hair cells (IHCs) of the cochlea transduce sound waves into an ionic (mainly potassium) current that leads to exocytosis of glutamate from the IHC and activation of postsynaptic type I afferent fibers of the radial ganglion (reviewed in Meyer and Moser 2010, Moser and Vogl 2016, Fettiplace 2017). IHCs have stereocilia on their apical surface that are arranged in rows of increasing height, a "staircase" arrangement. Stereocilia of different rows are connected by a tip link comprising a CDH23 dimer on the taller stereocilium bound to a PCDH15 dimer on the shorter stereocilium. PCDH15 interacts with LHFPL5, an auxiliary subunit of the mechanoelectrical transduction channel (MET channel, also called the mechanotransduction channel), which contains at least TMC1 (adults) or TMC2 (newborns), TMIE, and the auxiliary subunits LHFPL5 and CIB2 (reviewed in Fettiplace and Kim 2014, Fettiplace 2016).

Deflection of the stereocilia by sound waves creates tension on the tip link that increases the open probability of the MET channel, which then transports calcium and potassium ions from the scala media into the IHC, depolarizing the IHC (reviewed in Fettiplace 2017). The potassium channel KCNQ4 located in the neck region of the cell may also participate in depolarization. The depolarization of the IHC opens voltage-gated Cav1.3 channels (CACNA1D:CACA2D2:CACNB2) located in stripes near ribbon synapses on the basolateral surface of the IHC. The resulting localized influx of calcium ions activates exocytosis of glutamate into the synapse by an interaction between calcium and Otoferlin (OTOF) on glutamate-loaded vesicles in the IHC (reviewed in Wichmann 2015).

Ribbon synapses are characterized by a multiprotein complex, the ribbon, that contains at least BASSOON, RIBEYE (an isoform of CTBP2), and PICCOLINO (a small isoform of PICCOLO) and appears to act to transiently tether vesicles near the synapse and thereby increase the pool of readily releasable vesicles (reviewed in Safieddine et al. 2012, Wichman and Moser 2015, Pangrsic and Vogl 2018, Moser et al. 2020).

ATP2B1 calcium channels, ATP2B2 calcium channels, KCNMA1:KCNMB1:LRRRC52 potassium channels, and basolateral KCNQ4 potassium channels transport cations out of the IHC and thereby act to repolarize the cell and limit the duration of the synaptic potentials (reviewed in Patuzzi 2011, Oak and Yi 2014).

References

Wichmann C (2015). Molecularly and structurally distinct synapses mediate reliable encoding and processing of auditory information. *Hear. Res.*, 330, 178-90. [↗](#)

Moser T & Vogl C (2016). New insights into cochlear sound encoding. *F1000Res*, 5. [↗](#)

Fettiplace R (2016). Is TMC1 the Hair Cell Mechanotransducer Channel?. *Biophys. J.*, 111, 3-9. [↗](#)

Oak MH & Yi E (2014). Voltage-gated K(+) channels contributing to temporal precision at the inner hair cell-auditory afferent nerve fiber synapses in the mammalian cochlea. *Arch. Pharm. Res.*, 37, 821-33. [↗](#)

Kim KX & Fettiplace R (2014). The physiology of mechano-electrical transduction channels in hearing. *Physiol. Rev.*, 94, 951-86. [↗](#)

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2019-09-23	Edited	May B
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2 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 3 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
SPTBN1	Q01082	TRIOBP	Q9H2D6-4, Q9H2D6-5

4. Sensory processing of sound (R-HSA-9659379)

In mammals, sounds are processed in the cochlea, a spiral-shaped organ in the inner ear (reviewed in Basch et al. 2016, Fettiplace 2017, Koppl and Manley 2019). Low frequency sounds are sensed at the distal end (apex) of the cochlea; high frequency sounds are sensed at the proximal end (base) of the cochlea (reviewed in Dallos 1992, Manley 2018). Sound vibrations are transmitted from the eardrum through the three bones of the inner ear (malleus, incus, stapes) and the oval window of the cochlea to the fluids within the cochlea. Within the organ of Corti in the cochlea there are 3 rows of outer hair cells (OHCs) on the external side of the tunnel of Corti and 1 row of inner hair cells (IHCs) on the internal side (Spoendlin 1967). Each IHC synapses with approximately 20 afferent myelinated type I spiral ganglion neurons and functions as a sensory receptor to convert the energy of sound waves to secretion of glutamate neurotransmitter. Multiple OHCs synapse with each unmyelinated type II afferent neuron and OHCs are also synapsed with efferent medial olivocochlear fibers (Spoendlin 1967). The primary function of OHCs, however, is amplification of organ of Corti motions in response to sound (Ryan and Dallos 1975). Amplification is produced by changes in receptor-potential driven cell length caused by changes in the conformation of the unusual membrane protein prestin (SLC26A5, Zheng et al. 2000).

IHCs and OHCs sense the sonic vibrations by deflection of stereocilia on their apical surfaces (reviewed in Fettiplace et al. 2017, McPherson 2018). The stereocilia are arranged in rows of increasing height, with a stereocilium of one row connected to a stereocilium of another row by a tip link composed of a CDH23 dimer on the taller stereocilium joined at its N-termini to the N-termini of a PCDH15 dimer on the shorter stereocilium. CDH23 is connected to the cytoskeleton of the taller stereocilium via MYO7A (MyoVIIa), USH1C (Harmonin), and USH1G (Sans) (reviewed in Peng et al. 2011, Cosgrove and Zallochi 2014, Barr-Gillespie 2015, Fettiplace 2017, McGrath et al. 2017, Cunningham and Müller 2019, Ó Maoiléidigh and Ricci 2019, Velez-Ortega and Frolenkov 2019) while PCDH15 on the shorter stereocilium interacts with LHFPL5, an auxiliary subunit of the mechano-electrical transduction channel (MET channel, also known as the mechanotransduction channel), which contains at least TMC1 or TMC2, TMIE, and the auxiliary subunits LHFPL5 and CIB2 (reviewed in Fettiplace 2016, Qiu and Müller 2018, Corey et al. 2019). Deflection of stereocilia in the direction that increases tension on the tip link causes depolarization of the cell by increasing the open probability of the MET channel, which then transports calcium and potassium into the hair cell according to the gradient of those ions between the scala media (containing endolymph at 154 mM K⁺ and <1 mM Ca²⁺) at the apex of the cell and the scala tympani (containing perilymph at 7 mM K⁺) at the base (reviewed in Fettiplace and Kim 2014). Similarly, compression of the tip link by deflection of the stereocilia in the opposite direction decreases the open probability of the MET channel and causes hyperpolarization of the cell.

Depolarization of IHCs causes opening of voltage-gated calcium channels arrayed in stripes on the basolateral membrane close to ribbon synapses formed between the IHC and the afferent fiber of a myelinated type I spiral ganglion neuron. This results in a localized increase in cytosolic calcium ions which interact with Otoferlin (OTOF) on glutamate-containing synaptic vesicles at the ribbon structure to activate exocytosis of glutamate into the synapse formed with the afferent neuron (reviewed in Wichmann 2015, Pangrsic and Vogl 2018). Ribbon synapses are distinguished by electron-dense ribbon structures projecting from the presynaptic membrane into the cytosol and comprising at least BASSOON, RIBEYE (an isoform of CTBP2), and PICCOLINO (an isoform of PICCOLO). The ribbon structures appear to transiently bind synaptic vesicles and facilitate resupply of synaptic vesicles at active zones to refill the pool of readily releasable vesicles (reviewed in Moser et al. 2006, Moser et al. 2020).

In contrast with IHCs, OHCs mainly function in sound amplification by decreasing up to about 4% in length in response to depolarization caused by opening of the MET channel and increasing in length in response to hyperpolarization caused by channel closing, resulting in alternating compression and decompression between the reticular lamina and the basilar membrane. The changes in the length of the OHC are caused by very rapid (microseconds), voltage-sensitive changes in the conformation of the membrane protein prestin (SLC26A5). Stereociliary ATP2B2 (PMCA2) extrudes calcium ions and basally located KCNQ4 extrudes potassium ions to repolarize the OHC.

OHCs are synapsed with efferent cholinergic medial olivocochlear fibers (reviewed in Fritzsche and Elliott 2017, Fuchs and Lauer 2019). Acetylcholine released at the synapse binds an unusual, nicotine-antagonized, nicotinic receptor comprising CHRNA9 and CHRNA10. Upon binding acetylcholine, CHRNA9:CHRNA10 transports calcium ions into the OHC. The calcium activates SK2 potassium channels (KCNN2) and BK potassium channels (KCNMA1:KCNMB1) which extrude potassium ions, hyperpolarize the OHC, and inhibit activation of the OHC.

Loud sounds can cause a temporary threshold shift (temporary loss of hearing) caused by damage to stereocilia and synapses or permanent threshold shift (permanent loss of hearing) caused by damage or death of hair cells and neurons (reviewed in Kurabi et al. 2017).

References

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Fettiplace R (2016). Is TMC1 the Hair Cell Mechanotransducer Channel?. *Biophys. J.*, 111, 3-9.

Kim KX & Fettiplace R (2014). The physiology of mechano-electrical transduction channels in hearing. *Physiol. Rev.*, 94, 951-86.

Fettiplace R (2017). Hair Cell Transduction, Tuning, and Synaptic Transmission in the Mammalian Cochlea. *Compr Physiol*, 7, 1197-1227.

Zalocchi M & Cosgrove D (2014). Usher protein functions in hair cells and photoreceptors. *Int. J. Biochem. Cell Biol.*, 46, 80-9.

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2 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 3 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
SPTBN1	Q01082	TRIOBP	Q9H2D6-4, Q9H2D6-5

5. RHO GTPase cycle (R-HSA-9012999)

RHO family of GTPases is large and diverse, with many of its members considered to be master regulators of actin cytoskeleton. RHO GTPases are involved in the regulation of many cellular processes that depend on dynamic reorganization of the cytoskeleton, including cell migration, cell adhesion, cell division, establishment of cellular polarity and intracellular transport. As a consequence, RHO GTPases play important roles in neuronal development, immunity and cardio-vascular homeostasis. RHO GTPases are involved in the etiology of infectious diseases, congenital immunodeficiencies, neurodegenerative diseases and cancer. For review, please refer to Jaffe and Hall 2005, Lemichez and Aktories 2013, Ridley 2015, Hodge and Ridley 2016, Haga and Ridley 2016, Olson 2018, and Kalpachidou et al. 2019.

Phylogenetically, RHO GTPases can be grouped into four clusters. The first cluster consists of three subfamilies: Rho, RhoD/RhoF and Rnd. The second cluster consists of three subfamilies: Rac, Cdc42 and RhoU/RhoV. The third cluster consists of the RhoH subfamily. The fourth cluster consists of the RhoBTB subfamily. Miro GTPases and RHOBTB3 ATPase are sometimes described as Rho family members, but they are phylogenetically distant from the Rho family and constitute two separate families of Ras-like GTPases, which, besides Rho, Miro and RHOBTB3 also includes Ran, Arf, Rab and Ras families (Boureux et al. 2007). Based on their activation type, RHO GTPases can be divided into classical (typical) and atypical (reviewed by Haga and Ridley 2016, and Kalpachidou et al. 2019). Classical RHO GTPases cycle between active GTP-bound states and inactive GDP-bound states through steps that are tightly controlled by members of three classes of proteins: (1) guanine nucleotide dissociation inhibitors or GDIs, which maintain Rho proteins in an inactive state in the cytoplasm, (2) guanine nucleotide exchange factors or GEFs, which destabilize the interaction between Rho proteins and their bound nucleotide, the net result of which is the exchange of bound GDP for the more abundant GTP, and (3) GTPase activating proteins or GAPs, which stimulate the low intrinsic GTP hydrolysis activity of Rho family members, thus promoting their inactivation. GDIs, GEFs, and GAPs are themselves subject to tight regulation, and the overall level of Rho activ-

ity reflects the balance of their activities. Many of the Rho-specific GEFs, GAPs, and GDIs act on multiple Rho GTPases, so that regulation of these control proteins can have complex effects on the functions of multiple Rho GTPases (reviewed by Van Aelst and D'Souza-Schorey 1997, and Hodge and Ridley 2016). The classical Rho GTPase cycle is diagrammed in the figure below. External or internal cues promote the release of Rho GTPases from the GDI inhibitory complexes, which allows them to associate with the plasma membrane, where they are activated by GEFs (1), and can signal to effector proteins (4). Then, GAPs inactivate the GTPases by accelerating the intrinsic GTPase activity, leading to the GDP bound form (2). Once again, the GDI molecules stabilize the inactive GDP bound form in the cytoplasm, waiting for further instructions (3) (Tcherkezian and Lamarche-Vane, 2007). Classical RHO GTPases include four subfamilies: Rho (includes RHOA, RHOB and RHOC), Rac (includes RAC1, RAC2, RAC3 and RHOG), Cdc42 (includes CDC42, RHOJ and RHOQ) and RhoD/RhoF (includes RHOD and RHOF) (reviewed in Haga and Ridley 2016). RHOA, the founding member of the RHO GTPase family, regulates the actin cytoskeleton, formation of stress fibers and cell contractility, which is implicated in cell adhesion and migration (Lessey et al. 2012). RHOB and RHOC functions resemble RHOA (Vega and Ridley 2018; Guan et al. 2018). RHOB is also involved in membrane trafficking and DNA repair (Vega and Ridley 2018). RAC1 regulates the cytoskeleton and the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Acevedo and Gonzalez-Billault 2018), and is involved in cell adhesion and cell migration (Marei and Malliri 2017). RAC2 expression is restricted to hematopoietic cells and RAC2 is a component of the phagocytic oxidase complex in neutrophils (Troeger and Williams 2013). RAC3 shares 92% sequence identity with RAC1 and is highly expressed in neurons (de Curtis 2019). CDC42 regulate the cytoskeleton and cell polarity, and is involved in cell adhesion and migration as well as in intracellular membrane trafficking (Egorov and Polishchuk 2017; Xiao et al. 2018; Pichaud et al. 2019; Woods and Lew 2019). RHOJ is highly expressed in endothelial cells, regulating their motility and vascular morphogenesis (Leszczynska et al. 2011; Shi et al. 2016). RHOQ (also known as TC10) is highly activated on exocytosing vesicles and recycling endosomes (Donnelly et al. 2014) and is involved in trafficking of CFTR (cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator) (Cheng et al. 2005). RHOD regulates cytoskeletal dynamics and intracellular transport of vesicles (Randazzo 2003; Gad and Aspenstrom 2010; Aspenstrom et al. 2014, Aspenstrom et al. 2020). RHOF regulates cytoskeletal dynamics (Gad and Aspenstrom 2010; Aspenstrom et al. 2014, Aspenstrom et al. 2020) and promotes the formation of filopodia and stress fibers (Fan and Mellor 2012). RHOD and RHOF do possess GTPase activity and are therefore grouped with classical RHO GTPases, but they are atypical in the sense that they possess high intrinsic guanine nucleotide exchange activity and do not require GEFs for activation (Aspenstrom et al. 2020).

Atypical RHO GTPases do not possess GTPase activity. They therefore constitutively exist in the active GTP-bound state. Atypical RHO GTPases include three subfamilies: Rnd (includes RND1, RND2 and RND3), RhoBTB (includes RHOBTB1 and RHOBTB2), RhoH (RHOH is the only member) and RhoU/RhoV (includes RHOU and RHOV). RND1 and RND3 can antagonize RHOA activity, leading to loss of stress fibers and cell rounding (Haga and Ridley 2016). RND1, RND2 and RND3 regulate cell migration (Ridley 2015; Mouly et al. 2019). RHOBTB1 is a component of a signaling cascade that regulates vascular function and blood pressure (Ji and Rivero 2016). RHOBTB2 is involved in COP9 signalosome-regulated and CUL3-dependent protein ubiquitination (Berthold et al. 2008; Ji and Rivero 2016). RHOH expression is restricted to hematopoietic cells, and it is known to be involved in T cell receptor (TCR) signaling and T cell development (Suzuki and Oda 2008; Troeger and Williams 2013). RHOU and RHOV expression is induced by WNT signaling and they are involved in regulation of cell shape and cell adhesion (Faure and Fort 2015; and Hodge and Ridley 2016).

Almost every classical RHO GTPase interacts with multiple GEFs, GAPs and GDIs, and every RHO GTPase activates multiple downstream effectors. There are 82 Rho GEFs (71 Dbl, reviewed in Fort and Blangy 2017, and 11 DOCK, reviewed in Meller et al. 2005), 66 Rho GAPs (Amin et al. 2016) and 3 Rho GDIs (Dransart et al. 2005) encoded by the human genome. To keep our reaction annotations compact, we have grouped the GEF, GAP, GDI and effector proteins associated with each RHO GTPase into sets. Within a set, we have distinguished full set members from candidate members on the basis of the amount of experimental evidence supporting the member's molecular function. Note that members of a set can otherwise be functionally quite diverse. Annotation of upstream activators of GEFs, GAPs and GDIs was outside the scope of this catalogue pathway and is or will be shown elsewhere in Reactome. Signaling through downstream effectors is shown in more detail in the Reactome pathway "RHO GTPase Effectors".

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Edit history

Date	Action	Author
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ANLN	Q9NQW6	ARMC10	Q9UH62	GJA1	P17302
KCTD13	Q8WZ19	SPTBN1	Q01082		

6. Signaling by Rho GTPases (R-HSA-194315)

The Rho family of small guanine nucleotide binding proteins is one of seven phylogenetic branches of the Ras superfamily (Bernards 2005), which, besides Rho, Miro and RHOBTB3 also includes Ran, Arf, Rab and Ras families (Boueux et al. 2007). Miro GTPases and RHOBTB3 ATPase are sometimes described as Rho family members, but they are phylogenetically distinct (Boueux et al. 2007). Phylogenetically, RHO GTPases can be grouped into four clusters. The first cluster consists of three subfamilies: Rho, RhoD/RhoF and Rnd. The second cluster consists of three subfamilies: Rac, Cdc42 and RhoU/RhoV. The third cluster consists of the RhoH subfamily. The fourth cluster consists of the RhoBTB subfamily. Based on their activation type, RHO GTPases can be divided into classical (typical) and atypical (reviewed by Haga and Ridley 2016, and Kalpachidou et al. 2019). Classical RHO GTPases cycle between active GTP-bound states and inactive GDP-bound states through steps that are tightly controlled by members of three classes of proteins: (1) guanine nucleotide dissociation inhibitors or GDIs, which maintain Rho proteins in an inactive state in the cytoplasm, (2) guanine nucleotide exchange factors or GEFs, which destabilize the interaction between Rho proteins and their bound nucleotide, the net result of which is the exchange of bound GDP for the more abundant GTP, and (3) GTPase activating proteins or GAPs, which stimulate the low intrinsic GTP hydrolysis activity of Rho family members, thus promoting their inactivation. GDIs, GEFs, and GAPs are themselves subject to tight regulation, and the overall level of Rho activity reflects the balance of their activities. Many of the Rho-specific GEFs, GAPs, and GDIs act on multiple Rho GTPases, so that regulation of these control proteins can have complex effects on the functions of multiple Rho GTPases (reviewed by Van Aelst and D'Souza-Schorey 1997, Schmidt and Hall 2002, Jaffe and Hall 2005, Bernards 2005, and Hodge and Ridley 2016). Classical RHO GTPases include four subfamilies: Rho (includes RHOA, RHOB and RHOC), Rac (includes RAC1, RAC2, RAC3 and RHOG), Cdc42 (includes CDC42, RHOJ and RHOQ) and RhoD/RhoF (includes RHOD and RHOF) (reviewed in Haga and Ridley 2016). Atypical RHO GTPases do not possess GTPase activity. They therefore constitutively exist in the active GTP-bound state. Atypical RHO GTPases include three subfamilies: Rnd (includes RND1, RND2 and RND3), RhoBTB (includes RHOBTB1 and RHOBTB2), RhoH (RHOH is the only member) and RhoU/RhoV (includes RHOV and RHOV). Members of the Rho family have been identified in all eukaryotes. Among Rho GTPases, RHOA, RAC1 and CDC42 have been most extensively studied.

RHO GTPases regulate cell behavior by activating a number of downstream effectors that regulate cytoskeletal organization, intracellular trafficking and transcription (reviewed by Sahai and Marshall 2002). They are best known for their ability to induce dynamic rearrangements of the plasma membrane-associated actin cytoskeleton (Aspenstrom et al. 2004; Murphy et al. 1999; Govek et al. 2005). Beyond this function, Rho GTPases also regulate actomyosin contractility and microtubule dynamics. Rho mediated effects on transcription and membrane trafficking are believed to be secondary to these functions. At the more macroscopic level, Rho GTPases have been implicated in many important cell biological processes, including cell growth control, cytokinesis, cell motility, cell-cell and cell-extracellular matrix adhesion, cell transformation and invasion, and development (Govek et al., 2005). One of the best studied RHO GTPase effectors are protein kinases ROCK1 and ROCK2, which phosphorylate many proteins involved in the stabilization of actin filaments and generation of actin-myosin contractile force, such as LIM kinases and myosin regulatory light chains (MRLC) (reviewed in Riento and Ridley 2003). The p21-activated kinase family, which includes PAK1, PAK2 and PAK3, is another well characterized family of RHO GTPase effectors involved in cytoskeleton regulation (reviewed in Daniels and Bokoch 1999, Szczepanowska 2009). Protein kinase C related kinases (PKNs), PKN1, PKN2 and PKN3 play important roles in cytoskeleton organization (Hamaguchi et al. 2000), regulation of cell cycle (Misaki et al. 2001), receptor trafficking (Metzger et al. 2003), apoptosis (Takahashi et al. 1998), and transcription (Metzger et al. 2003, Metzger et al. 2005, Metzger et al. 2008). Citron kinase (CIT) is involved in Golgi apparatus organization through regulation of the actin cytoskeleton (Camera et al. 2003) and in the regulation of cytokinesis (Gruneberg et al. 2006, Bassi et al. 2013, Watanabe et al. 2013). Kinectin (KTN1), a kinesin anchor protein, is a RHO GTPase effector involved in kinesin-mediated vesicle motility (Vignal et al. 2001, Hotta et al. 1996), including microtubule-dependent lysosomal transport (Vignal et al. 2001). IQGAP proteins, IQGAP1, IQGAP2 and IQGAP3, are RHO GTPase effectors that modulate cell shape and motility through regulation of G-actin/F-actin equilibrium (Brill et al. 1996, Fukata et al. 1997, Bashour et al. 1997, Wang et al. 2007, Pelikan-Conchaudron et al. 2011), regulate adherens junctions (Kuroda et al. 1998, Hage et al. 2009), and contribute to cell polarity and lamellipodia formation (Fukata et al. 2002, Suzuki and Takahashi 2008). WASP and WAVE proteins (reviewed by Lane et al. 2014), as well as formins (reviewed by Kuhn and Geyer 2014), are RHO GTPase effectors that regulate actin polymerization and play important roles in cell motility, organelle trafficking and mitosis. Rhotekin (RTKN) and rhophilins (RHPN1 and RHPN2) are RHO GTPase effectors that regulate the organization of the actin cytoskeleton and are implicated in the establishment of cell polarity, cell motility and possibly endosome trafficking (Sudo et al. 2006, Watanabe et al. 1996, Fujita et al. 2000, Peck et al. 2002, Mircescu et al. 2002). Cytoskeletal changes triggered by the activation of formins (Miralles et al. 2003) and RTKN (Reynaud et al. 2000) may lead to stimulation of SRF-mediated transcription. NADPH oxidase complexes 1, 2 and 3 (NOX1, NOX2 and NOX3), membrane associated enzymatic complexes that use NADPH as an electron donor to reduce oxygen and produce superoxide (O₂⁻), are also regulated by RHO GTPases (Knaus et al. 1991, Roberts et al. 1999, Kim and Dinauer 2001, Jyoti et al. 2014, Cheng et al. 2006, Miyano et al. 2006, Ueyama et al. 2006). Every RHO GTPase activates multiple downstream effectors and most effectors are regulated by multiple RHO GTPases, resulting in an elaborate cross-talk.

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Edit history

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Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
ANLN	Q9NQW6	ARMC10	Q9UH62	DVL3	Q92997
GJA1	P17302	KCTD13	Q8WZ19	SPTBN1	Q01082

7. Signaling by Rho GTPases, Miro GTPases and RHOBTB3 (R-HSA-9716542)

RAS-like proteins are small GTP binding proteins characterized structurally by 5 G boxes that are involved in nucleotide binding and hydrolysis. RAS-like proteins are typically active when bound to GTP and inactive when bound to GDP. Conversion between the two states is mediated by effector proteins: among others, GTPase activating proteins (GAPs) enable hydrolysis of bound GTP to form GDP, which remains bound, and guanine nucleotide exchange factors (GEFs) enable exchange of bound GDP for free GTP (intracellular GTP concentrations are typically an order of magnitude higher than GDP concentrations) (reviewed in Tetlow and Tamanoi, 2013).

The human genome includes over 150 members of the RAS superfamily grouped into five main subfamilies: RAS, RHO, ARF, RAB and RAN. These small GTPases affect a wide range of critical processes including gene expression, signal transduction, cell morphology, vesicle and nuclear trafficking, cellular proliferation and motility, among others (reviewed in Tetlow and Tamanoi, 2013).

The RHO family of GTPases is large and diverse, with many of its members considered to be master regulators of actin cytoskeleton, involved in the regulation of cellular processes that depend on dynamic reorganization of the cytoskeleton, including cell migration, cell adhesion, cell division, establishment of cellular polarity and intracellular transport (reviewed in Hodge and Ridley 2016, and Olson 2018).

MIRO proteins and RHOBTB3 protein, sometimes called atypical RHO proteins, show a high degree of overall sequence similarity to members of the five RAS-like subfamilies but diverge in their functions enough to constitute two separate subfamilies (Boureux et al. 2007). MIRO proteins have intrinsically high GTPase activity and do not require GTPase activator proteins (Peters et al. 2018). They play an important role mitochondrial biogenesis, maintenance and organization (reviewed in Birsa et al. 2013). The GTPase domain of RHOBTB3 is divergent from other Ras like superfamily members and displays ATPase activity (Espinosa et al. 2009). RHOBTB3 is involved in CUL3 dependent protein ubiquitination (Berthold et al. 2008; Ji and Rivero 2016), retrograde transport from endosomes to the Golgi apparatus (Espinosa et al. 2009), regulation of the cell cycle and in modulating the adaptive response to hypoxia (Ji and Rivero 2016).

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Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2021-02-17	Authored	Rothfels K
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2022-11-19	Modified	Wright A

6 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 6 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
ANLN	Q9NQW6	ARMC10	Q9UH62	DVL3	Q92997
GJA1	P17302	KCTD13	Q8WZ19	SPTBN1	Q01082

8. Cell-Cell communication (R-HSA-1500931)

Cell-to-Cell communication is crucial for multicellular organisms because it allows organisms to coordinate the activity of their cells. Some cell-to-cell communication requires direct cell-cell contacts mediated by receptors on their cell surfaces. Members of the immunoglobulin superfamily (IgSF) proteins are some of the cell surface receptors involved in cell-cell recognition, communication and many aspects of the axon guidance and synapse formation-the crucial processes during embryonal development (Rougon & Hobert 2003).

Processes annotated here as aspects of **cell junction organization** mediate the formation and maintenance of adherens junctions, tight junctions, and gap junctions, as well as aspects of cellular interactions with extracellular matrix and hemidesmosome assembly. **Nephrin protein family interactions** are central to the formation of the slit diaphragm, a modified adherens junction. Interactions among members of the **signal regulatory protein family** are important for the regulation of migration and phagocytosis by myeloid cells.

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KIRREL3	Q6UWL6, Q8IZU9	SPTBN1	Q01082

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 2 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
LTBP3	Q14767, Q9NS15

10. Elastic fibre formation (R-HSA-1566948)

Cellular compartments: extracellular region.

Elastic fibres (EF) are a major structural constituent of dynamic connective tissues such as large arteries and lung parenchyma, where they provide essential properties of elastic recoil and resilience. EF are composed of a central cross-linked core of elastin, surrounded by a mesh of microfibrils, which are composed largely of fibrillin. In addition to elastin and fibrillin-1, over 30 ancillary proteins are involved in mediating important roles in elastic fibre assembly as well as interactions with the surrounding environment. These include fibulins, elastin microfibril interface located proteins (EMILINs), microfibril-associated glycoproteins (MAGPs) and Latent TGF-beta binding proteins (LTBPs). Fibulin-5 for example, is expressed by vascular smooth muscle cells and plays an essential role in the formation of elastic fibres through mediating interactions between elastin and fibrillin (Yanigasawa et al. 2002, Freeman et al. 2005). In addition, it plays a role in cell adhesion through integrin receptors and has been shown to influence smooth muscle cell proliferation (Yanigasawa et al. 2002, Nakamura et al. 2002). EMILINs are a family of homologous glycoproteins originally identified in extracts of aortas. Found at the elastin-fibrillin interface, early studies showed that antibodies to EMILIN can affect the process of elastic fibre formation (Bressan et al. 1993). EMILIN1 has been shown to bind elastin and fibulin-5 and appears to coordinate their common interaction (Zanetti et al. 2004). MAGPs are found to co-localize with microfibrils. MAGP-1, for example, binds strongly to an N-terminal sequence of fibrillin-1. Other proteins found associated with microfibrils include vitronectin (Dahlback et al. 1990).

Fibrillin is most familiar as a component of elastic fibres but microfibrils with no elastin are found in the ciliary zonules of the eye and invertebrate circulatory systems. The addition of elastin to microfibrils is a vertebrate adaptation to high pulsatile pressures in their closed circulatory systems (Faury et al. 2003). Elastin appears to have emerged after the divergence of jawless vertebrates from other vertebrates (Sage 1982).

Fibrillin-1 is the major structural component of microfibrils. Fibrillin-2 is expressed earlier in development than fibrillin-1 and may be important for elastic fiber formation (Zhang et al. 1994). Fibrillin-3 arose as a duplication of fibrillin-2 that did not occur in the rodent lineage. It was first isolated from human brain (Corson et al. 2004).

Fibrillin assembly is not as well defined as elastin assembly. The primary structure of fibrillin is dominated by calcium binding epidermal growth factor like repeats (Kielty et al. 2002). Fibrillin may form dimers or trimers before secretion. However, multimerisation predominantly occurs outside the cell. Formation of fibrils appears to require cell surface structures suggesting an involvement of cell surface receptors. Fibrillin is assembled pericellularly (i.e. on or close to the cell surface) into microfibrillar arrays that undergo time dependent maturation into microfibrils with beaded-string appearance. Transglutaminase forms gamma glutamyl epsilon lysine isopeptide bonds within or between peptide chains. Additionally, intermolecular disulfide bond formation between fibrillins is an important contributor to fibril maturation (Reinhardt et al. 2000).

Models of fibrillin-1 microfibril structure suggest that the N-terminal half of fibrillin-1 is asymmetrically exposed in outer filaments, while the C-terminal half is buried in the interior (Kuo et al. 2007). Fibrillinopathies include Marfan syndrome, familial ectopia lentis, familial thoracic aneurysm, all due to mutations in the fibrillin-1 gene FBN1, and congenital contractural arachnoidactyly which is caused by mutation of FBN2 (Maslen & Glanville 1993, Davis & Summers 2012).

In vivo assembly of fibrillin requires the presence of extracellular fibronectin fibres (Sabatier et al. 2009). Fibrillins have Arg-Gly-Asp (RGD) sequences that interact with integrins (Pfaff et al. 1996, Sakamoto et al. 1996, Bax et al., 2003, Jovanovic et al. 2008) and heparin-binding domains that interact with a cell-surface heparan sulfate proteoglycan (Tiedemann et al. 2001) possibly a syndecan (Ritty et al. 2003). Fibrillins also have a major role in binding and sequestering growth factors such as TGF beta into the ECM (Neptune et al. 2003). Proteoglycans such as versican (Isogai et al. 2002), biglycan, and decorin (Reinboth et al. 2002) can interact with the microfibrils. They confer specific properties including hydration, impact absorption, molecular sieving, regulation of cellular activities, mediation of growth factor association, and release and transport within the extracellular matrix (Buczek-Thomas et al. 2002). In addition, glycosaminoglycans have been shown to interact with tropoelastin through its lysine side chains (Wu et al. 1999), regulating tropoelastin assembly (Tu & Weiss 2008).

Elastin is synthesized as a 70kDa monomer called tropoelastin, a highly hydrophobic protein composed largely of two types of domains that alternate along the polypeptide chain. Hydrophobic domains are rich in glycine, proline, alanine, leucine and valine. These amino acids occur in characteristic short (3-9 amino acids) tandem repeats, with a flexible and highly dynamic structure (Floquet et al. 2004). Unlike collagen, glycine in elastin is not rigorously positioned every 3 residues. However, glycine is distributed frequently throughout all hydrophobic domains of elastin, and displays a strong preference for inter-glycine spacing of 0-3 residues (Rauscher et al. 2006).

Elastic fibre formation involves the deposition of tropoelastin onto a template of fibrillin rich microfibrils. Recent results suggest that the first step of elastic fiber formation is the organization of small globules of elastin on the cell surface followed by globule aggregation into microfibrils (Kozel et al. 2006). An important contribution to the initial stages assembly is thought to be made by the intrinsic ability of the protein to direct its own polymeric organization in a process termed 'coacervation' (Bressan et al. 1986). This self-assembly process appears to be determined by interactions between hydrophobic domains (Bressan et al. 1986, Vrhovski et al. 1997, Bellingham et al. 2003, Cirulis & Keeley 2010) which result in alignment of the cross-linking domains, allowing the stabilization of elastin through the formation of cross-links generated through the oxidative deamination of lysine residues, catalyzed by members of the lysyl oxidase (LOX) family (Reiser et al. 1992, Mithieux & Weiss 2005). The first step in the cross-linking reaction is the oxidative formation of the delta aldehyde, known as alpha amino adipic semialdehyde or allysine (Partridge 1963). Subsequent reactions that are probably spontaneous lead to the formation of cross-links through dehydrolysinonorleucine and allysine aldol, a trifunctional cross-link dehydromerodesmosine and two tetrafunctional cross-links desmosine and isodesmosine (Lucero & Kagan 2006), which are unique to elastin. These cross-links confer mechanical integrity and high durability. In addition to their role in self-assembly, hydrophobic domains provide elastin with its elastomeric properties, with initial studies suggesting that the elastomeric properties of elastin are driven through changes in entropic interactions with surrounding water molecules (Hoeve & Flory 1974).

A very specific set of proteases, broadly grouped under the name elastases, is responsible for elastin remodelling (Antonicelli et al. 2007). The matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) are particularly important in elastin breakdown, with MMP2, 3, 9 and 12 explicitly shown to degrade elastin (Ra & Parks 2007). Nonetheless, elastin typically displays a low turnover rate under normal conditions over a lifetime (Davis 1993).

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Knutsen RH, Little CD, Rongish BJ, Davis EC, Kozel BA, Levy MA, ... Wagenseil JE (2006). Elastic fiber formation: a dynamic view of extracellular matrix assembly using timer reporters. *J Cell Physiol*, 207, 87-96. [↗](#)

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LTBP3	Q14767, Q9NS15

11. Nuclear signaling by ERBB4 (R-HSA-1251985)

Besides signaling as a transmembrane receptor, ligand activated homodimers of ERBB4 JM-A isoforms (ERBB4 JM-A CYT1 and ERBB4 JM-A CYT2) undergo proteolytic cleavage by ADAM17 (TACE) in the juxtamembrane region, resulting in shedding of the extracellular domain and formation of an 80 kDa membrane bound ERBB4 fragment known as ERBB4 m80 (Rio et al. 2000, Cheng et al. 2003). ERBB4 m80 undergoes further proteolytic cleavage, mediated by the gamma-secretase complex, which releases the soluble 80 kDa ERBB4 intracellular domain, known as ERBB4 s80 or E4ICD, into the cytosol (Ni et al. 2001). ERBB4 s80 is able to translocate to the nucleus, promote nuclear translocation of various transcription factors, and act as a transcription co-factor. In neuronal precursors, ERBB4 s80 binds the complex of TAB and NCOR1, helps to move the complex into the nucleus, and is a co-factor of TAB:NCOR1-mediated inhibition of expression of astrocyte differentiation genes GFAP and S100B (Sardi et al. 2006). In mammary cells, ERBB4 s80 recruits STAT5A transcription factor in the cytosol, shuttles it to the nucleus, and acts as the STAT5A co-factor in binding to and promoting transcription from the beta-casein (CSN2) promoter, and may be involved in the regulation of other lactation-related genes (Williams et al. 2004, Muraoka-Cook et al. 2008). ERBB4 s80 was also shown to bind activated estrogen receptor in the nucleus and act as its transcriptional co-factor in promoting transcription of some estrogen-regulated genes, such as progesterone receptor gene NR3C3 and CXCL12 i.e. SDF1 (Zhu et al. 2006). ERBB4s80 may inhibit transcription of telomerase reverse transcriptase (TERT) by increasing methylation of the TERT gene promoter through an unknown mechanism (Ishibashi et al. 2012).

The C-tail of ERBB4 possesses several WW-domain binding motifs (three in CYT1 isoform and two in CYT2 isoform), which enable interaction of ERBB4 with WW-domain containing proteins. ERBB4 s80, through WW-domain binding motifs, interacts with YAP1 transcription factor, a known proto-oncogene, and may be a co-regulator of YAP1-mediated transcription (Komuro et al. 2003, Omerovic et al. 2004). The tumor suppressor WWOX, another WW-domain containing protein, competes with YAP1 in binding to ERBB4 s80 and prevents translocation of ERBB4 s80 to the nucleus (Aqeilan et al. 2005). ERBB4 s80 is also able to translocate to the mitochondrial matrix, presumably when its nuclear translocation is inhibited. Once in the mitochondrion, the BH3 domain of ERBB4, characteristic of BCL2 family members, may enable it to act as a pro-apoptotic factor (Naresh et al. 2006).

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STMN1	P16949

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STMN1	ENSG00000117632

12. TGF-beta receptor signaling activates SMADs (R-HSA-2173789)

Binding of transforming growth factor beta 1 (TGF beta 1, i.e. TGFB1) to TGF beta receptor type 2 (TGFBR2) activates TGF beta receptor signaling cascade. TGFB1 is posttranslationally processed by furin (Dubois et al. 1995) to form a homodimer and secreted to the extracellular space as part of the large latent complex (LLC). After the LLC disassembles in the extracellular space, dimeric TGFB1 becomes capable of binding to TGFBR2 (Annes et al. 2003, Keski Oja et al. 2004). Formation of TGFB1:TGFBR2 complex creates a binding pocket for TGF-beta receptor type-1 (TGFBR1) and TGFBR1 is recruited to the complex by binding to both TGFB1 and TGFBR2. This results in an active heterotetrameric TGF-beta receptor complex that consists of TGFB1 homodimer bound to two heterodimers of TGFBR1 and TGFBR2 (Wrana et al. 1992, Moustakas et al. 1993, Franzen et al. 1993). TGF-beta signaling can also occur through a single heterodimer of TGFBR1 and TGFBR2, although with decreased efficiency (Huang et al. 2011). TGFBR1 and TGFBR2 interact through their extracellular domains, which brings their cytoplasmic domains together. Ligand binding to extracellular receptor domains is cooperative, but no conformational change is seen from crystal structures of either TGFB1- or TGFB3-bound heterotetrameric receptor complexes (Groppe et al. 2008, Radaev et al. 2010).

Activation of TGFBR1 by TGFBR2 in the absence of ligand is prevented by FKBP1A (FKBP12), a peptidyl-prolyl cis-trans isomerase. FKBP1A forms a complex with inactive TGFBR1 and dissociates from it only after TGFBR1 is recruited by TGFB1-bound TGFBR2 (Chen et al. 1997).

Both TGFBR1 and TGFBR2 are receptor serine/threonine kinases. Formation of the hetero-tetrameric TGF-beta receptor complex (TGFBR) in response to TGFB1 binding induces receptor rotation, so that TGFBR2 and TGFBR1 cytoplasmic kinase domains face each other in a catalytically favourable configuration. TGFBR2 trans-phosphorylates serine residues at the conserved Gly-Ser-rich juxtapositioned domain (GS domain) of TGFBR1 (Wrana et al. 1994, Souchelnytskyi et al. 1996), activating TGFBR1.

In addition to phosphorylation, TGFBR1 may also be sumoylated in response to TGF-beta stimulation. Sumoylation enhances TGFBR1 kinase activity (Kang et al. 2008).

The activated TGFBR complex is internalized by clathrin-mediated endocytosis into early endosomes. With the assistance of SARA, an early endosome membrane protein, phosphorylated TGFBR1 within TGFBR complex recruits SMAD2 and/or SMAD3, i.e. R-SMADs (Tsukazaki et al. 1998). TGFBR1 phosphorylates recruited SMAD2/3 on two C-terminal serine residues (Souchelnytskyi et al. 2001). The phosphorylation changes the conformation of SMAD2/3 MH2 domain, promoting dissociation of SMAD2/3 from SARA and TGFBR1 (Souchelnytskyi et al. 1997, Macias-Silva et al. 1996, Nakao et al. 1997) and formation of SMAD2/3 trimers (Chacko et al. 2004). The phosphorylated C-terminal tail of SMAD2/3 has high affinity for SMAD4 (Co-SMAD), inducing formation of SMAD2/3:SMAD4 heterotrimers, composed of two phosphorylated R-SMADs (SMAD2 and/or SMAD3) and SMAD4 (Co-SMAD). SMAD2/3:SMAD4 heterotrimers are energetically favored over R-SMAD trimers (Nakao et al. 1997, Qin et al. 2001, Kawabata et al. 1998, Chacko et al. 2004).

SMAD2/3:SMAD4 heterotrimers translocate to the nucleus where they act as transcriptional regulators.

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1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 2 Reactome entities

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LTBP3	Q14767, Q9NS15

13. Degradation of DVL (R-HSA-4641258)

DVL protein levels are regulated by both proteasomal and lysosomal degradation (reviewed in Gao and Chen, 2010). The E3 ligases HECCF1, ITCH and KLHL12:CUL3 have all been shown to contribute to the polyubiquitination and subsequent degradation of DVL (Angers et al, 2006; Miyazaki et al, 2004; Wei et al, 2012). DVL stability is also regulated by its interaction with DACT1, which promotes degradation of DVL in the lysosome (Cheyette et al, 2002; Zhang et al, 2006).

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2 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 2 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
DVL3	Q92997	KLHL12	Q53G59

14. Transport of connexins along the secretory pathway (R-HSA-190827)

Cellular compartments: cytosol.

Connexins follow the classical secretory transport route from the ER to the plasma membrane: ER -> ERGIC -> Golgi -> TGN (Trans Golgi Network) -> PM (Plasma Membrane). All connexins assemble or oligomerize into hexameric connexons. The site of assembly varies and depends on Cx isoform, or cell type (see Koval et al., 2006).

Oligomerization of connexins has been observed during ER membrane insertion (Cx32), just after exit from the ER, in the ER-Golgi-intermediate compartment (Cx26) and inside the Trans-Golgi Network (Cx43) (Falk et al. 1997; Ahmad et al. 1999; Musil and Goodenough 1993; Diez et al. 1999).

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GJA1	P17302

15. Oligomerization of connexins into connexons (R-HSA-190704)

The mechanism of connexin assembly into connexons has been well characterized. Two different types of connexons can be formed. A connexon containing six identical connexin molecules is referred to as an homomeric connexon, while a connexon containing at least two different connexin molecules is referred to as an heteromeric connexon. The connexin molecules making up an heteromeric connexon appear to belong to only one subgroup (alpha or beta); heteromeric connexons containing both alpha and beta subunits have not yet been observed. Indeed, an intrinsic signal in four amino acid positions appears to confer different physicochemical characteristics to certain connexins in the alpha and beta groups (Lagr et al., 2003). These intrinsic signals are Cx specific, however (see Gemel et al., 2006). Therefore, additional yet unknown signals are required to regulate connexin compatibility and hetero-oligomerization.

The identification of the subcellular location at which gap junction assembly occurs has proven difficult. One explanation for this difficulty may be that the location of oligomerization for each connexon varies depending upon Cx type or cell type. Oligomerization has been observed after ER membrane insertion (Cx43, Cx32, Cx26) (Falk et al., 1997; Ahmad et al., 1999; Ahmad and Evans, 2002), in the ER-Golgi-intermediate compartment (ERGIC) (Cx32) (Diez et al. 1999) and inside the trans-Golgi network (Cx43) (Musil and Goodenough, 1993).

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GJA1	P17302

16. Negative regulation of TCF-dependent signaling by DVL-interacting proteins (R-HSA-5368598)

Cellular compartments: cytosol.

DVL is a central component of WNT signaling that plays roles in both canonical and non-canonical pathways (reviewed in Gao and Chen, 2010). In the canonical pathway, DVL recruits AXIN from the destruction complex upon WNT stimulation, allowing cytosolic beta-catenin to accumulate (reviewed in MacDonald et al, 2009). DVL activity is regulated by phosphorylation as well as by regulated proteasomal or lysosomal degradation (reviewed in Gao and Chen, 2010). In addition, DVL activity can be regulated by interaction with other proteins; both CXXC4 and CCDC88C were identified as negative regulators of WNT signaling that interact directly with DVL, although the role of these proteins in limiting WNT signaling remain to be fully worked out (Hino et al, 2001; Oshita et al, 2003; Ekici et al, 2010; Ishida-Takagishi et al, 2012).

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1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 1 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
DVL3	Q92997

17. Signaling by ERBB4 (R-HSA-1236394)

Cellular compartments: cytosol, extracellular region, plasma membrane.

ERBB4, also known as HER4, belongs to the ERBB family of receptors, which also includes ERBB1 (EGFR/HER1), ERBB2 (HER2/NEU) and ERBB3 (HER3). Similar to EGFR, ERBB4 has an extracellular ligand binding domain, a single transmembrane domain and a cytoplasmic domain which contains an active tyrosine kinase and a C-tail with multiple phosphorylation sites. At least three and possibly four splicing isoforms of ERBB4 exist that differ in their C-tail and/or the extracellular juxtamembrane regions: ERBB4 JM-A CYT1, ERBB4 JM-A CYT2 and ERBB4 JM-B CYT1 (the existence of ERBB4 JM-B CYT2 has not been confirmed).

ERBB4 becomes activated by binding one of its seven ligands, three of which, HB-EGF, epiregulin, EPR and betacellulin BTC, are EGF-like (Elenius et al. 1997, Riese et al. 1998), while four, NRG1, NRG2, NRG3 and NRG4, belong to the related neuregulin family (Tzahar et al. 1994, Carraway et al. 1997, Zhang et al. 1997, Hayes et al. 2007). Upon ligand binding, ERBB4 forms homodimers (Sweeney et al. 2000) or it heterodimerizes with ERBB2 (Li et al. 2007). Dimers of ERBB4 undergo trans-autophosphorylation on tyrosine residues in the C-tail (Cohen et al. 1996, Kaushansky et al. 2008, Hazan et al. 1990, Li et al. 2007), triggering downstream signaling cascades. The pathway Signaling by ERBB4 only shows signaling by ERBB4 homodimers. Signaling by heterodimers of ERBB4 and ERBB2 is shown in the pathway Signaling by ERBB2. Ligand-stimulated ERBB4 is also able to form heterodimers with ligand-stimulated EGFR (Cohen et al. 1996) and ligand-stimulated ERBB3 (Riese et al. 1995). Dimers of ERBB4 with EGFR and dimers of ERBB4 with ERBB3 were demonstrated in mouse cell lines in which human ERBB4 and EGFR or ERBB3 were exogenously expressed. These heterodimers undergo trans-autophosphorylation. The promiscuous heteromerization of ERBBs adds combinatorial diversity to ERBB signaling processes. As ERBB4 binds more ligands than other ERBBs, but has restricted expression, ERBB4 expression channels responses to ERBB ligands. The signaling capabilities of the four receptors have been compared (Schulze et al. 2005).

As for other receptor tyrosine kinases, ERBB4 signaling effectors are largely dictated through binding of effector proteins to ERBB4 peptides that are phosphorylated upon ligand binding. All splicing isoforms of ERBB4 possess two tyrosine residues in the C-tail that serve as docking sites for SHC1 (Kaushansky et al. 2008, Pinkas-Kramarski et al. 1996, Cohen et al. 1996). Once bound to ERBB4, SHC1 becomes phosphorylated on tyrosine residues by the tyrosine kinase activity of ERBB4, which enables it to recruit the complex of GRB2 and SOS1, resulting in the guanyl-nucleotide exchange on RAS and activation of RAF and MAP kinase cascade (Kainulainen et al. 2000).

The CYT1 isoforms of ERBB4 also possess a C-tail tyrosine residue that, upon trans-autophosphorylation, serves as a docking site for the p85 alpha subunit of PI3K (Kaushansky et al. 2008, Cohen et al. 1996), leading to assembly of an active PI3K complex that converts PIP2 to PIP3 and activates AKT signaling (Kainulainen et al. 2000).

Besides signaling as a conventional transmembrane receptor kinase, ERBB4 differs from other ERBBs in that JM-A isoforms signal through efficient release of a soluble intracellular domain. Ligand-activated homodimers of ERBB4 JM-A isoforms (ERBB4 JM-A CYT1 and ERBB4 JM-A CYT2) undergo proteolytic cleavage by ADAM17 (TACE) in the juxtamembrane region, resulting in shedding of the extracellular domain and formation of an 80 kDa membrane bound ERBB4 fragment known as ERBB4 m80 (Rio et al. 2000, Cheng et al. 2003). ERBB4 m80 undergoes further proteolytic cleavage, mediated by the gamma-secretase complex, which releases the soluble 80 kDa ERBB4 intracellular domain, known as ERBB4 s80 or E4ICD, into the cytosol (Ni et al. 2001). ERBB4 s80 is able to translocate to the nucleus, promote nuclear translocation of various transcription factors, and act as a transcription co-factor. For example, in mammary cells, ERBB4 binds SH2 transcription factor STAT5A. ERBB4 s80 shuttles STAT5A to the nucleus, and acts as a STAT5A co-factor in binding to and promoting transcription from the beta-casein (CSN2) promoter, and may be involved in the regulation of other lactation-related genes (Jones et al. 1999, Williams et al. 2004, Muraoka-Cook et al. 2008). ERBB4 s80 binds activated estrogen receptor in the nucleus and acts as a transcriptional co-factor in promoting transcription of some estrogen-regulated genes, including progesterone receptor gene NR3C3 and CXCL12 (SDF1) (Zhu et al. 2006). In neuronal precursors, ERBB4 s80 binds the complex of TAB and NCOR1, helps to move the complex into the nucleus, and is a co-factor of TAB:NCOR1-mediated inhibition of expression of astrocyte differentiation genes GFAP and S100B (Sardi et al. 2006).

The C-tail of ERBB4 possesses several WW-domain binding motifs (three in CYT1 isoform and two in CYT2 isoform), which enable interaction of ERBB4 with WW-domain containing proteins. ERBB4 s80, through WW-domain binding motifs, interacts with YAP1 transcription factor, a known proto-oncogene, and is a co-regulator of YAP1-mediated transcription in association with TEAD transcription factors (Komuro et al. 2003, Omerovic et al. 2004). Hence, the WW binding motif couples ERBB4 to the major effector arm of the HIPPO signaling pathway. The tumor suppressor WWOX, another WW-domain containing protein, competes with YAP1 in binding to ERBB4 s80 and prevents translocation of ERBB4 s80 to the nucleus (Aqeilan et al. 2005).

WW-domain binding motifs in the C-tail of ERBB4 play an important role in the downregulation of ERBB4 receptor signaling, enabling the interaction of intact ERBB4, ERBB4 m80 and ERBB4 s80 with NEDD4 family of E3 ubiquitin ligases WWP1 and ITCH. The interaction of WWP1 and ITCH with intact ERBB4 is independent of receptor activation and autophosphorylation. Binding of WWP1 and ITCH ubiquitin ligases leads to ubiquitination of ERBB4 and its cleavage products, and subsequent degradation through both proteasomal and lysosomal routes (Omerovic et al. 2007, Feng et al. 2009). In addition, the s80 cleavage product of ERBB4 JM-A CYT-1 isoform is the target of NEDD4 ubiquitin ligase. NEDD4 binds ERBB4 JM-A CYT-1 s80 (ERBB4jmAcyt1s80) through its PIK3R1 interaction site and mediates ERBB4jmAcyt1s80 ubiquitination, thereby decreasing the amount of ERBB4jmAcyt1s80 that reaches the nucleus (Zeng et al. 2009).

ERBB4 also binds the E3 ubiquitin ligase MDM2, and inhibitor of p53 (Arasada et al. 2005). Other proteins that bind to ERBB4 intracellular domain have been identified by co-immunoprecipitation and mass spectrometry (Gilmore-Hebert et al., 2010), and include transcriptional co-repressor TRIM28/KAP1, which promotes chromatin compaction. DNA damage signaling through ATM releases TRIM28-associated heterochromatinization. Interactions of ERBB4 with TRIM28 and MDM2 may be important for integration of growth factor responses and DNA damage responses.

In human breast cancer cell lines, ERBB4 activation enhances anchorage-independent colony formation in soft agar but inhibits cell growth in a monolayer culture. Different ERBB4 ligands induce different gene expression changes in breast cancer cell lines. Some of the genes induced in response to ERBB4 signaling in breast cancer cell lines are RAB2, EPS15R and GATA4. It is not known if these genes are direct transcriptional targets of ERBB4 (Amin et al. 2004).

Transcriptome and ChIP-seq comparisons of full-length and intracellular domain isoforms in isogenic MCF10A mammary cell background have revealed the diversification of ERBB4 signaling engendered by alternative splicing and cleavage (Wali et al., 2014). ERBB4 broadly affected protease expression, cholesterol biosynthesis, HIF1-alpha signaling, and HIPPO signaling pathways, and other pathways were differentially activated by CYT1 and CYT2 isoforms. For example, CYT1 promoted expression of transcription factors TWIST1 and SNAIL1 that promote epithelial-mesenchymal transition. HIF1-alpha and HIPPO signaling are mediated, respectively, by binding of ERBB4 to HIF1-alpha and to YAP (Paatero et al., 2012, Komuro et al., 2003). ERBB4 increases activity of the transcription factor SREBF2, resulting in increased expression of SREBF2-target genes involved in cholesterol biosynthesis. The mechanism is not known and may involve facilitation of SREBF2 cleavage through ERBB4-mediated PI3K signaling (Haskins et al. 2016).

In some contexts, ERBB4 promotes growth suppression or apoptosis (Penington et al., 2002). Activation of ERBB4 in breast cancer cell lines leads to JNK dependent increase in BRCA1 mRNA level and mitotic cell cycle delay, but the exact mechanism has not been elucidated (Muraoka Cook et al. 2006). The nature of growth responses may be connected with the spliced isoforms expressed. In comparisons of CYT1 vs CYT2 (full-length and ICD) expression in mammary cells, CYT1 was a weaker growth inducer, associated with attenuated MAPK signaling relative to CYT2 (Wali et al., 2014). ERBB4 s80 is also able to translocate to the mitochondrial matrix, presumably when its nuclear translocation is inhibited. Once in the mitochondrion, the BH3 domain of ERBB4, characteristic of BCL2 family members, may enable it to act as a pro apoptotic factor (Naresh et al. 2006).

ERBB4 plays important roles in the developing and adult nervous system. Erbb4 deficiency in somatostatin-expressing neurons of the thalamic reticular nucleus alters behaviors dependent on sensory selection (Ahrens et al. 2015). NRG1-activated ERBB4 signaling enhances AMPA receptor responses through PKC-dependent AMPA receptor exocytosis. This results in an increased excitatory input to parvalbumin-expressing inhibitory neurons in the visual cortex and regulates visual cortical plasticity (Sun et al. 2016). NRG1-activated ERBB4 signaling is involved in GABAergic activity in amygdala which mediates fear conditioning (fear memory) (Lu et al. 2014). Conditional Erbb4 deletion from fast-spiking interneurons, chandelier and basket cells of the cerebral cortex leads to synaptic defects associated with increased locomotor activity and abnormal emotional, social and cognitive function that can be linked to some of the schizophrenia features. The level of GAD1 (GAD67) protein is reduced in the cortex of conditional Erbb4 mutants. GAD1 is a GABA synthesizing enzyme. Cortical mRNA levels of GAD67 are consistently decreased in schizophrenia (Del Pino et al. 2014). Erbb4 is expressed in the GABAergic neurons of the bed nucleus stria terminalis, a part of the extended amygdala. Inhibition of NRG1-triggered ERBB4 signaling induces anxiety-like behavior, which depends on GABAergic neurotransmission. NRG1-ERBB4 signaling stimulates presynaptic GABA release, but the exact mechanism is not known (Geng et al. 2016). NRG1 protects cortical interneurons against ischemic brain injury through ERBB4-mediated increase in GABAergic transmission (Guan et al. 2015). NRG2-activated ERBB4 can reduce the duration of GABAergic transmission by binding to GABA receptors at the postsynaptic membrane via their GABRA1 subunit and promoting endocytosis of GABA receptors (Mitchell et al. 2013). NRG1 promotes synchronization of prefrontal cortex interneurons in an ERBB4 dependent manner (Hou et al. 2014). NRG1-ERBB4 signaling protects neurons from the cell death induced by a mutant form of the amyloid precursor protein (APP) (Woo et al. 2012).

Clinical relevance of ERBB4 has been identified in several contexts. In cancer, putative and validated gain-of-function mutations or gene amplification that may be drivers have been identified at modest frequencies, and may also contribute to resistance to EGFR and ERBB2-targeted therapies. This is noteworthy as ERBB4 kinase activity is inhibited by pan-ERBB tyrosine kinase inhibitors, including lapatinib, which is approved by the US FDA. The reduced prevalence relative to EGFR and ERBB2 in cancer may reflect more restricted expression of ERBB4, or differential signaling, as specific ERBB4 isoforms have been linked to growth inhibition or apoptosis in experimental systems. ERBB2/ERBB4 heterodimers protect cardiomyocytes, so reduced activity of ERBB4 in patients treated with the ERBB2-targeted therapeutic antibody trastuzumab may contribute to the cardiotoxicity of this agent when used in combination with (cardiotoxic) anthracyclines.

With the importance of ERBB4 in developing and adult nervous system, NRG1 and/or ERBB4 polymorphisms, splicing aberrations and mutations have been linked to nervous system disorders including schizophrenia and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, although these findings are not yet definitive.

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Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2011-03-25	Created	Orlic-Milacic M
2011-11-04	Authored	Orlic-Milacic M
2011-11-07	Edited	Matthews L, D'Eustachio P
2011-11-11	Reviewed	Zeng F, Harris RC
2012-02-20	Reviewed	Earp HS 3rd, Misiorek AM
2018-06-28	Revised	Orlic-Milacic M
2019-02-21	Revised	Stern DF
2019-02-21	Authored	Stern DF
2019-03-06	Edited	Orlic-Milacic M
2022-11-23	Modified	Wright A

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 2 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
STMN1	P16949

Input	Ensembl Id
STMN1	ENSG00000117632

18. Regulation of gap junction activity (R-HSA-191650)

Cellular compartments: plasma membrane.

Src is believed to suppress gap junction communication by phosphorylating Cx43.

The kinases c-Src (Giepmans et al. 2001; Sorgen et al. 2004), PKc (Lin et al. 2003) and MAPK (Mograb et al. 2003) play an essential role in the phosphorylation of Cx which leads to its degradation. c-Src appears to associate with and phosphorylate Cx43 leading to closure of gap junctions. Evidence suggests that v-src may activate MAPK, which in turn phosphorylates Cx43 on serine sites leading to channel gating (Zhou et al. 1999).

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Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2007-01-03	Authored	Gilleron J, Segretain D, Falk MM
2007-01-23	Created	Matthews L
2007-04-17	Edited	Matthews L
2022-11-19	Modified	Wright A

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 1 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
GJA1	P17302

19. SARS-CoV-2 targets PDZ proteins in cell-cell junction (R-HSA-9705677)

Diseases: COVID-19.

PSD95/Dlg1/ZO-1 (PDZ) domains are protein-protein recognition sequences, consisting of 80–90 amino acids that bind to a PDZ-binding motif (PBM), usually located at the end of the carboxy-terminus of a target protein (Hung AY & Sheng M 2002; Gerek ZN et al. 2009; Munz M et al. 2012). Proteins containing PDZ domains are typically found in the cell cytoplasm or in association with the plasma membrane and play a role in a variety of cellular processes such as cell-cell junctions, cellular polarity, and signal transduction pathways. The multidomain structure of PDZ-containing proteins enables them to interact with multiple binding partners simultaneously, thereby assembling larger protein complexes (Harris BZ & Lim WA 2001). Viruses also encode PBM-containing proteins that bind to cellular PDZ proteins. Viral PBMs target cellular PDZ-containing proteins involved in tight junction formation, cell polarity establishment, and apoptosis (Javier RT & Rice AP 2011).

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Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2020-10-28	Created	Shamovsky V
2021-10-27	Authored	Shamovsky V
2022-02-18	Edited	Shamovsky V
2022-02-18	Reviewed	Messina F

Date	Action	Author
2022-03-01	Modified	Shamovsky V

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 1 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
GJA1	P17302

20. Signal Transduction (R-HSA-162582)

Signal transduction is a process in which extracellular signals elicit changes in cell state and activity. Transmembrane receptors sense changes in the cellular environment by binding ligands, such as hormones and growth factors, or reacting to other types of stimuli, such as light. Stimulation of transmembrane receptors leads to their conformational change which propagates the signal to the intracellular environment by activating downstream signaling cascades. Depending on the cellular context, this may impact cellular proliferation, differentiation, and survival. On the organism level, signal transduction regulates overall growth and behavior.

Receptor tyrosine kinases (RTKs) transmit extracellular signals by phosphorylating their protein partners on conserved tyrosine residues. Some of the best studied RTKs are EGFR (reviewed in Avraham and Yarden, 2011), FGFR (reviewed in Eswarakumar et al, 2005), insulin receptor (reviewed in Saltiel and Kahn, 2001), NGF (reviewed in Reichardt, 2006), PDGF (reviewed in Andrae et al, 2008) and VEGF (reviewed in Xie et al, 2004). RTKs frequently activate downstream signaling through RAF/MAP kinases (reviewed in McKay and Morrison, 2007 and Wellbrock et al 2004), AKT (reviewed in Manning and Cantley, 2007) and PLC- gamma (reviewed in Patterson et al, 2005), which ultimately results in changes in gene expression and cellular metabolism.

Receptor serine/threonine kinases of the TGF-beta family, such as TGF-beta receptors (reviewed in Kang et al. 2009) and BMP receptors (reviewed in Miyazono et al. 2009), transmit extracellular signals by phosphorylating regulatory SMAD proteins on conserved serine and threonine residues. This leads to formation of complexes of regulatory SMADs and SMAD4, which translocate to the nucleus where they act as transcription factors.

WNT receptors transmit their signal through beta-catenin. In the absence of ligand, beta-catenin is constitutively degraded in a ubiquitin-dependent manner. WNT receptor stimulation releases beta-catenin from the destruction complex, allowing it to translocate to the nucleus where it acts as a transcriptional regulator (reviewed in MacDonald et al, 2009 and Angers and Moon, 2009). WNT receptors were originally classified as G-protein coupled receptors (GPCRs). Although they are structurally related, GPCRs primarily transmit their signals through G-proteins, which are trimers of alpha, beta and gamma subunits. When a GPCR is activated, it acts as a guanine nucleotide exchange factor, catalyzing GDP to GTP exchange on the G-alpha subunit of the G protein and its dissociation from the gamma-beta heterodimer. The G-alpha subunit regulates the activity of adenylate cyclase, while the gamma-beta heterodimer can activate AKT and PLC signaling (reviewed in Rosenbaum et al. 2009, Oldham and Hamm 2008, Ritter and Hall 2009).

NOTCH receptors are activated by transmembrane ligands expressed on neighboring cells, which results in cleavage of NOTCH receptor and release of its intracellular domain. NOTCH intracellular domain translocates to the nucleus where it acts as a transcription factor (reviewed in Kopan and Ilgan, 2009).

Integrins are activated by extracellular matrix components, such as fibronectin and collagen, leading to conformational change and clustering of integrins on the cell surface. This results in activation of integrin-linked kinase and other cytosolic kinases and, in co-operation with RTK signaling, regulates survival, proliferation and cell shape and adhesion (reviewed in Hehlhans et al, 2007) .

Besides inducing changes in gene expression and cellular metabolism, extracellular signals that trigger the activation of Rho GTP-ases can trigger changes in the organization of cytoskeleton, thereby regulating cell polarity and cell-cell junctions (reviewed in Citi et al, 2011).

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Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2005-04-01	Created	Joshi-Tope G
2005-05-06	Authored	Joshi-Tope G, Charalambous M, Gopinathrao G, Rothfels K, Bevan AP et al.
2022-11-17	Reviewed	Barroso I, Rush MG, Joutel A, Stanley FM
2022-11-19	Modified	Wright A

9 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 11 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
ANLN	Q9NQW6	ARMC10	Q9UH62	DVL3	Q92997
GJA1	P17302	KCTD13	Q8WZ19	KLHL12	Q53G59
LTBP3	Q14767, Q9NS15	SPTBN1	Q01082	STMN1	P16949

Input	Ensembl Id
STMN1	ENSG00000117632

21. Signaling by TGF-beta Receptor Complex (R-HSA-170834)

The TGF-beta/BMP pathway incorporates several signaling pathways that share most, but not all, components of a central signal transduction engine. The general signaling scheme is rather simple: upon binding of a ligand, an activated plasma membrane receptor complex is formed, which passes on the signal towards the nucleus through a phosphorylated receptor SMAD (R-SMAD). In the nucleus, the activated R-SMAD promotes transcription in complex with a closely related helper molecule termed Co-SMAD (SMAD4). However, this simple linear pathway expands into a network when various regulatory components and mechanisms are taken into account. The signaling pathway includes a great variety of different TGF-beta/BMP superfamily ligands and receptors, several types of the R-SMADs, and functionally critical negative feedback loops. The R-SMAD:Co-SMAD complex can interact with a great number of transcriptional co-activators/co-repressors to regulate positively or negatively effector genes, so that the interpretation of a signal depends on the cell-type and cross talk with other signaling pathways such as Notch, MAPK and Wnt. The pathway plays a number of different biological roles in the control of embryonic and adult cell proliferation and differentiation, and it is implicated in a great number of human diseases.

TGF beta (TGFB1) is secreted as a homodimer, and as such it binds to TGF beta receptor II (TGFBR2), inducing its dimerization. Binding of TGF beta enables TGFBR2 to form a stable hetero-tetrameric complex with TGF beta receptor I homodimer (TGFBR1). TGFBR2 acts as a serine/threonine kinase and phosphorylates serine and threonine residues within the short GS domain (glycine-serine rich domain) of TGFBR1.

The phosphorylated heterotetrameric TGF beta receptor complex (TGFBR) internalizes into clathrin coated endocytic vesicles where it associates with the endosomal membrane protein SARA. SARA facilitates the recruitment of cytosolic SMAD2 and SMAD3, which act as R-SMADs for TGF beta receptor complex. TGFBR1 phosphorylates recruited SMAD2 and SMAD3, inducing a conformational change that promotes formation of R-SMAD trimers and dissociation of R-SMADs from the TGF beta receptor complex.

In the cytosol, phosphorylated SMAD2 and SMAD3 associate with SMAD4 (known as Co-SMAD), forming a heterotrimer which is more stable than the R-SMAD homotrimers. R-SMAD:Co-SMAD heterotrimer translocates to the nucleus where it directly binds DNA and, in cooperation with other transcription factors, regulates expression of genes involved in cell differentiation, in a context-dependent manner.

The intracellular level of SMAD2 and SMAD3 is regulated by SMURF ubiquitin ligases, which target R-SMADs for degradation. In addition, nuclear R-SMAD:Co-SMAD heterotrimer stimulates transcription of inhibitory SMADs (I-SMADs), forming a negative feedback loop. I-SMADs bind the phosphorylated TGF beta receptor complexes on caveolin coated vesicles, derived from the lipid rafts, and recruit SMURF ubiquitin ligases to TGF beta receptors, leading to ubiquitination and degradation of TGFBR1. Nuclear R-SMAD:Co-SMAD heterotrimers are targets of nuclear ubiquitin ligases which ubiquitinate SMAD2/3 and SMAD4, causing heterotrimer dissociation, translocation of ubiquitinated SMADs to the cytosol and their proteasome-mediated degradation. For a recent review of TGF-beta receptor signaling, please refer to Kang et al. 2009.

References

Kang JS, Derynck R & Liu C (2009). New regulatory mechanisms of TGF-beta receptor function. *Trends Cell Biol*, 19, 385-94. [↗](#)

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2006-01-18	Created	Jassal B
2006-02-02	Authored	Jassal B, Moustakas A, Heldin CH, Huminiecki L
2006-04-18	Edited	Jassal B
2006-04-18	Reviewed	Heldin CH
2012-04-05	Revised	Orlic-Milacic M
2012-04-10	Edited	Jassal B
2012-05-14	Reviewed	Huang T
2012-11-14	Reviewed	Chen YG
2022-11-19	Modified	Wright A

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 2 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
LTBP3	Q14767, Q9NS15

22. Formation of annular gap junctions (R-HSA-196025)

Gap junction plaque internalization and the disruption cell communication requires a reorganization of Cx molecular interactions. Proteins including Dab-2, AP-2, Dynamin and Myosin VI associate with gap junction plaques permitting the internalisation of plaques after clathrin association (Piehl et al., 2007). Until now, two kinds of annular gap junctions have been described. The first is a small vesicle like structure which permits gap junction plaque renewal without arrest of functionality (Jordan et al., 2001). The second is a large annular structure, composed primarily of the junctional plaques of two adjacent cells (Jordan et al., 2001; Segretain et al., 2004).

Until now, two kinds of annular gap junctions have been described. The first is a small vesicle like structure which permits gap junction plaque renewal without arrest of functionality [Jordan et al., 2001]. The second is a large annular structure, composed primarily of the junctional plaques of two adjacent cells (Jordan et al., 2001; Segretain et al., 2004).

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Gumpert A, Segretain D, Falk MM, Piehl M, Denizot JP & Lehmann C (2007). Internalization of Large Double-Membrane Intercellular Vesicles by a Clathrin-dependent Endocytic Process. *Mol Biol Cell*. [↗](#)

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2007-01-03	Authored	Gilleron J, Segretain D, Falk MM
2007-04-17	Created	Matthews L
2022-11-19	Modified	Wright A

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 1 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
GJA1	P17302

23. WNT mediated activation of DVL (R-HSA-201688)

The three human Dishevelled (DVL) proteins play a central and overlapping role in the transduction of the WNT signaling cascade (Lee et al, 2008; reviewed in Gao and Chen 2010). DVL activity is regulated by phosphorylation, although the details are not completely worked out. DVL likely exists as a phosphoprotein even in the absence of WNT stimulation, and is further phosphorylated upon ligand binding. Casein kinase 1epsilon (CSNK1E), casein kinase 2 (CSNK2) and PAR1 have all been reported to phosphorylate DVL (Willert et al, 1997; Sun et al, 2001; Cong et al, 2004; Ossipova et al, 2005). Upon pathway activation, phosphorylated DVL translocates to the plasma membrane through an interaction between the DVL PDZ domain and the FZD KTxxxW motif (Wong et al, 2003; Umbhauer et al, 2000; Kikuchi et al, 2011). At the plasma membrane, DVL is believed to oligomerize through its DIX domain, providing a platform for AXIN recruitment; recruitment of AXIN is also facilitated by interaction with LRP (Schwarz-Romond et al, 2007; Mao et al, 2001). DVL interacts with phosphatidylinositol-4-kinase type II (PI4KII) and phosphatidylinositol-4-phosphate 5-kinase type I (PIP5KI) to promote formation of phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate (PI(4,5)P2) in the membrane, which is required for the clustering and phosphorylation of LRP6 and the recruitment of AXIN (Pan et al, 2008; Qin et al, 2009).

References

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Edit history

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2007-09-04	Edited	Matthews L
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2013-08-24	Authored	Rothfels K
2013-10-03	Edited	Gillespie ME
2014-01-22	Reviewed	Rajakulendran N
2014-02-15	Reviewed	van Amerongen R
2014-04-22	Reviewed	Kikuchi A
2022-11-19	Modified	Wright A

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 1 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
DVL3	Q92997

24. Gap junction degradation (R-HSA-190873)

The half-life of Cx is very short (1 to 5h) compared to other junctional proteins (Laird et al., 1995 ; Fallon and Goudenough, 1981). Connexins are targeted for degradation by the proteasome and the lysosome. Degradation appears to involve the phosphorylation of Connexins as well as their interactions with other proteins (Piehl et al., 2007).

References

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Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2007-01-03	Authored	Gilleron J, Segretain D, Falk MM
2007-01-09	Created	Matthews L
2007-03-27	Edited	Matthews L
2022-11-19	Modified	Wright A

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 1 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
GJA1	P17302

Input	UniProt Id
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25. Signaling by TGFB family members (R-HSA-9006936)

The human genome encodes 33 TGF-beta family members, including TGF-beta itself, as well as bone morphogenetic protein (BMP), activin, nodal and growth and differentiation factors (GDFs). This superfamily of ligands generally binds as dimers to hetero-tetrameric cell-surface receptor serine/threonine kinases to activate SMAD-dependent and SMAD-independent signaling (reviewed in Morikawa et al, 2016; Budi et al, 2017).

Signaling by the TGF-beta receptor complex is initiated by TGF-beta. TGF-beta (TGFB1), secreted as a homodimer, binds to TGF-beta receptor II (TGFB2), inducing its dimerization and formation of a stable hetero-tetrameric complex with TGF-beta receptor I homodimer (TGFB1). TGFB2-mediated phosphorylation of TGFB1 triggers internalization of the heterotetrameric TGF beta receptor complex (TGFB) into clathrin coated endocytic vesicles and recruitment of cytosolic SMAD2 and SMAD3, which act as R-SMADs for TGF beta receptor complex. TGFB1 phosphorylates SMAD2 and SMAD3, promoting their association with SMAD4 (known as Co-SMAD). In the nucleus, the SMAD2/3:SMAD4 heterotrimer binds target DNA elements and, in cooperation with other transcription factors, regulates expression of genes involved in cell differentiation. For a review of TGF-beta receptor signaling, please refer to Kang et al. 2009.

Signaling by BMP is triggered by bone morphogenetic proteins (BMPs). BMPs can bind type I receptors in the absence of type II receptors, but the presence of both types dramatically increases binding affinity. The type II receptor kinase transphosphorylates the type I receptor, leading to recruitment and phosphorylation of SMAD1, SMAD5 and SMAD8, which function as R-SMADs in BMP signalling pathways. Phosphorylated SMAD1, SMAD5 and SMAD8 form heterotrimeric complexes with SMAD4, the only Co-SMAD in mammals. The SMAD1/5/8:SMAD4 heterotrimer regulates transcription of genes involved in development of many tissues, including bone, cartilage, blood vessels, heart, kidney, neurons, liver and lung. For review of BMP signaling, please refer to Miyazono et al. 2010.

Signaling by activin is triggered when an activin dimer (activin A, activin AB or activin B) binds the type II receptor (ACVR2A, ACVR2B). This complex then interacts with the type I receptor (ACVR1B, ACVR1C) and phosphorylates it. The phosphorylated type I receptor phosphorylates SMAD2 and SMAD3. Dimers of phosphorylated SMAD2/3 bind SMAD4 and the resulting ternary complex enters the nucleus and activates target genes. For a review of activin signaling, please refer to Chen et al. 2006.

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Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2017-05-24	Edited	Rothfels K
2017-05-24	Authored	Rothfels K
2017-05-24	Created	Rothfels K
2017-06-22	Reviewed	D'Eustachio P
2022-11-19	Modified	Wright A

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 2 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
LTBP3	Q14767, Q9NS15

6. Identifiers found

Below is a list of the input identifiers that have been found or mapped to an equivalent element in Reactome, classified by resource.

18 of the submitted entities were found, mapping to 22 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
ANLN	Q9NQW6	ARMC10	Q9UH62	ASB1	Q9Y576
DES	P17661	DVL3	Q92997	EPB41L2	O43491
GJA1	P17302	KCTD13	Q8WZ19	KIF23	Q02241
KIRREL3	Q6UWL6, Q8IZU9	KLHL12	Q53G59	LTBP3	Q14767, Q9NS15
PACSIN2	Q9UNF0	SH3BP4	Q9P0V3	SPTBN1	Q01082
STMN1	P16949	TRIOBP	Q9H2D6-4, Q9H2D6-5	TLL9	Q3SXZ7

Input	Ensembl Id
STMN1	ENSG00000117632

7. Identifiers not found

These 6 identifiers were not found neither mapped to any entity in Reactome.

CY TSA

ECM2

KLHL8

RGPD5

SNX4

WDR90